

Effect of improved variety and water management practices on wet season rice crop in north Bihar, India.

Year	Total rainfall in season (cm)	Number of observations in each block	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) in different blocks			Total irrigation on water depth (cm)		WUE ^a (t ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)			Saving in water consumption (cm ha ⁻¹)
			Study	Control	CD (P=0.05)	Study	Control	Study	Control	CD (P=0.05)	
1989	142.0	18	3.7	1.9	0.14	24.4	46.7	1.4	0.4	0.06	22.3
1990	91.4	9	2.8	1.9	0.51	19.3	29.9	1.4	0.6	0.07	10.6
1991	89.1	9	3.7	3.2	0.33	41.3	91.0	0.9	0.3	0.10	49.7
1992	58.4	6	2.0	1.8	0.21	31.8	44.8	0.6	0.4	0.08	13.0
1993	138.2	15	3.2	2.2	0.31	18.0	18.0	1.7	1.2	0.04	0.0
1994	96.6	9	3.1	2.4	0.33	21.0	32.0	1.0	0.6	0.05	11.0

^aWUE = water use efficiency.

The results indicated that grain yield in the study fields averaged 34% more than in the control fields. The mean depth of irrigation water ranged from 18.0 to 41.3 cm in the study fields and 18.0 to 91.0 cm in the control fields.

The WUE also differed significantly, with higher values in the study fields than in the control fields. On average, yearly water consumption was 18.1 cm more in the control fields than in the study fields.

Improved rice varieties with improved water management practices can substantially increase yield as well as WUE on farms with irrigation. ■

On-farm water management studies in summer rice

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To demonstrate the significance of improved water management practices in rice cultivation, we conducted one large-scale experiment during the 1990-93 summer (Feb-May) seasons in farmers' fields using one of the minor canals off the main canal of the Ukai-Kakrapar command area in Gujarat. The clay soil was representative of those in the area for salinity and sodicity. The infiltration rate of the soil was 2.5 mm d⁻¹.

In the study plot (SP), 5 ± 2 cm of irrigation water was applied 1 d after standing water disappeared; in the control plot (CP), farmers' practices were followed. Water depth in SP was observed using graduated, colored wooden pegs and the water application was measured using Parshall flumes installed in the canal. Water depth, measured periodically in CP, averaged 10±2 cm more across the crop growth period. No rain was received during any of the cropping seasons.

Based on the mean results (see table), 29% of the irrigation water normally used by farmers was saved, with about 55% higher yield per unit of water applied by adopting the improved water management practices. The yield increase (estimated by a

standard crop-cutting experimental technique) in SP was about 10.3% more than in CP. The increase could be attributed to the alternate wetting and drying in the treated plot, which might have resulted in better nutrient availability and less accumulation of toxic gases.

During the past 3 yr, 15% more area was brought under cultivation, especially at the end of the minor canal. Based on this research, irrigation authorities were convinced that the rice crop does not require continuous flooding at the usual higher water depths. Farmers did not experience yield reduction by using less water. Irrigating the extra 15% area used the same quantity of water normally allotted to the minor canal. ■

Response of rice to water management practices. Gujarat, India. 1990-91 and 1993.

Item	1990		1991		1993		Mean	
	SP ^a	CP ^a	SP	CP	SP	CP	SP	CP
Total rice area (ha)	34.2	10.2	28.5	9.6	25.6	11.1	29.4	10.4
Total irrigation water (mm ha ⁻¹) ^b	984	1580	1231	1762	1376	1717	1197	1686
Yield of rice (t ha ⁻¹)	5.988	6.037	6.715	6.130	7.179	5.855	6.627	6.007
WUE ^c of applied water	6.1	3.8	5.4	3.5	5.2	3.4	5.5	3.5
Water saved over control (%)	37.7		30.1		19.8		29.0	
WUE ^c improved over control (%)	57.7		56.6		52.8		55.3	

^aSP = study plot; CP = control plot. ^bIrrigation applied excluded the water requirement for raising seedling, puddling the field, and preparing the land. ^cWUE = water use efficiency.